

THE CARBOrefit[®] METHOD – STRENGTHENING WITH TRC

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ABSTRACT

For the increasingly important preservation of existing structures, strengthening with carbon reinforced concrete has proven to be an effective option in recent years. With the CARBOrefit[®] process, this type of flexural strengthening has been approved by the building authorities in Germany. Thin layers of carbon reinforced concrete are applied to existing concrete structures for repair or to increase the load-bearing capacity. The materials, the dimensioning and the procedure, including the boundary conditions, are described in the general technical approval with the number Z-31.10-182 (DIBt, 2021) and are presented in this article. In addition, the requirements for contractors are specified.

KEYWORDS

Flexural strengthening; carbon reinforced concrete; general technical approval

INTRODUCTION

When it comes to tackling the biggest challenge of our time – climate change – the most sustainable solution in terms of construction is to use existing structures for as long as possible. Compared to demolition and new construction, this can save significant amounts of resources and minimise CO₂ emissions. As more than 50% of all CO₂ emissions are caused by construction alone (Weidner et al., 2021), the preservation of existing buildings represents a major environmental lever.

In Europe and especially in Germany, the goal has been announced to build a large number of affordable, climate-friendly homes in the coming years, e.g. 400,000 homes per year in Germany (Bundesstiftung Baukultur, 2022/23). At the same time, there will be a switch to a climate-neutral energy supply. This means that the proportion of energy used in construction will become a decisive factor in assessing the environmental sustainability of buildings. To enable this change, a fundamental rethink is needed in the construction sector.

However, from a conservation point of view it cannot be assumed that a building will not suffer any damage during its lifetime, so maintenance or refurbishment may be required. It may also be necessary to increase the load-bearing capacity of a structural component by strengthening it. Compared to conventional methods, such as CFRP lamellas or shotcrete, carbon concrete has been developed in recent years as an efficient alternative. In comparison, it is possible to increase the load-bearing capacity of old structures by up to 300-400% (Müller et al., 2020), while saving more than 85% of resources and 52% of CO₂ emissions (Schumann et al., 2021). In addition, the carbon fibres used are highly durable and resistant to almost all media.

However, carbon concrete is not yet state of the art and can therefore only be used in Germany with a general technical approval or a general type approval. This has been made possible by the general technical approval Z-31.10-182 (DIBt, 2021), the result of many years of intensive research. In this approval, the CARBOrefit[®] process for the flexural strengthening of reinforced concrete with carbon concrete is described and approved for use by the highest building authority, the German Institute for Building Technology (DIBt).

CONCRETE

The strengthening layer consists of CARBOrefit®-fine-grained concrete with embedded reinforcement of a high strength, non-corrosive carbon grid. The reinforcement absorbs tensile forces due to component stress, while the concrete provides the bond to the existing cross-section and can absorb compressive forces. The strengthening is applied in layers.

To match the small mesh size of the textile reinforcement, the concrete has a maximum grain size of 1 mm and can be applied to the surfaces to be strengthened by either spraying or laminating. This can be done in all directions, especially overhead. The fine concrete consists of cement, silica fume, fly ash and quartz sand and has the properties listed in Table 1 after 28 days (tested on 40x40x160 mm prisms).

Table 1: Characteristics of the CARBOrefit®-fine-grained concrete, according to (DIBt, 2021)

Characteristics	Unit	Value
Compressive strength (characteristic value after 28 days)	[MPa]	≥ 80
Flexural tensile strength (characteristic value after 28 days)	[MPa]	≥ 6
E-modulus (mean value after 28 days)	[MPa]	≥ 25.000

Due to the high tensile strength, the fine-meshed carbon grids arranged over a large area and the low dead weight of the strengthening layer, there is a sufficient bond to the old concrete section to eliminate the need for dowelling.

In addition, due to the low layer thickness, less moisture is added to the building and the clearance remains almost unchanged. Due to the chemically inert carbon reinforcement, more sustainable concrete compositions will also be possible in the future (Schneider et al., 2017).

REINFORCEMENT

The first approval for the carbon concrete strengthening process in Germany was granted in 2014. Since then, the carbon reinforcement has been continuously developed and the tensile and composite properties have been significantly improved. In 2021, the approval was fundamentally restructured and extended to include the optimised materials.

Basically, carbon reinforcement consists of up to 50,000 individual filaments that are impregnated to form a yarn. The yarns are then processed into grids with warp and weft directions. There are a number of different types of reinforcement that can be used, depending on the level of strengthening required and the application. The standard design as an axial grid is shown in Figure 1, left. The cross-sectional area of the yarn in the warp direction is 140 mm²/m. If a smaller cross-sectional area or a biaxial grid is required, it is possible to adapt the geometry of the grid with the special design, see Figure 1, right. In this way, the required reinforcement can be precisely matched to the boundary conditions of the strengthening operation. The properties of the fabrics are summarised in Table 2.

Figure 1: Carbon grid geometries in the approval; left: standard design, right: special design, according to (Wagner et al., 2022)

Table 2: Geometric properties of the standard design and special design grids in the approval, according to (DIBt, 2021)

Version	Property	Unit	Warp Yarn	Weft Yarn
Standard	Fiber content	[K]	≥ 48 and ≤ 50	12
	Cross-sectional area of the yarns	[mm ²]	≥ 1.8 and ≤ 1.95	0.45
	Yarn spacing	[mm]	12.7	16 +0/-2
Special	Fiber content	[K]	≥ 48 and ≤ 50	≥ 48 and ≤ 50
	Cross-sectional area of the yarns	[mm ²]	≥ 1.8 and ≤ 1.95	≥ 48 and ≤ 50
	Yarn spacing	[mm]	≥ 12.7 and ≤ 50.8	≥ 16 +0/-2 and smaller than twice the yarn distance in warp direction
	Additional requirements	[-]		$\geq 20\%$ of the cross-sectional area in warp direction

In addition to the variation in geometry, the approval provides for a differentiation of the yarns into Type 1 and Type 3 in terms of mechanical properties, Type 2 will follow. The different types provide different tensile strengths, bond strengths and stiffnesses (flexibility). Film forming dispersions are used as impregnating agents under defined manufacturing conditions. The design tensile strength of Type 3 is 1300 MPa, approximately three times the design tensile strength of reinforcing steel. This demonstrates the superior performance of carbon concrete over a shotcrete strengthening layer. The mechanical properties are summarised in Table 3.

Table 3: Mechanical properties of the different CARBOrefit®-grids, according to (DIBt, 2021)

Property	Unit	Type 1	Type 3
Characteristic tensile strength	[MPa]	1550	2250
Design tensile strength	[MPa]	768	1300
E-modulus	[MPa]	206.667	206.667
Max. strengthening force	[kN/m]	430	430
Design bond force	[N/mm]	0.564	4.7
Anchoring length (for full design stress)	[mm]	2450	500
Flexibility	[-]	very bendable	less bendable

In order to determine the design values, reduction factors have been introduced to take account of the various influences on material behaviour. These factors also reflect the improved mechanical properties of Type 3 compared to Type 1. The reductions due to long-term load, temperature (at 40°C) and chemical resistance are significantly lower. The high performance of the new carbon fabrics leads to a more economical dimensioning of the strengthening measure. Table 4 shows the reduction factors, distinguishing between tensile strength and bond.

Table 4: Reduction factors for Type 1 and Type 3, according to (DIBt, 2021)

Reduction Factors	Type 1	Type 3
Tensile strength		
Temperature influence (40 °C)	0.85	1.00
Long-term load	0.70	0.70
Durability	1.00	1.00
Bond strength		
Temperature influence (40°C)	0.45	1.00
Long-term load	0.47	0.70
Durability	1.00	1.00

The properties given in this table can be achieved using reinforcement products with different carbon fibres, impregnations and manufacturers. The designer must select a suitable type according to the approval and an economical reinforcement product for the measure.

TERMS AND CONDITIONS OF USE

In particular, the general technical approval regulates all product characteristics relevant to the building authorities. This includes the areas of use, storage, labelling, transport and confirmation of conformity. In addition, the connection to a structural system is regulated in the general type approval (Alfes et al., 2023).

The boundary conditions allow uniaxial strengthening in bending in the tension zone of reinforced concrete components. The warp direction of the carbon grid must be aligned with the load transmitting direction of the member. Good bonding conditions are achieved by carefully preparing the surface by cleaning, roughening and pre-wetting. To guarantee adequate adhesion, a characteristic adhesive strength of 1.0 MPa must also be verified on the member to be strengthened. The existing concrete must be normal concrete of maximum strength class C50/60 (characteristic cylinder compressive strength 50 MPa, characteristic cube compressive strength 60 MPa). In addition, the diameter or equivalent diameter of the existing steel reinforcement used must not exceed 20 mm. A minimum concrete cover of 10 mm is required.

At present, the application of the approval is limited to interior structures with predominantly static loads. Strengthening in bending intended for these structures may only be used in areas where shear reinforcement is not required by design. During use, the maximum temperature must not exceed 40°C and the relative humidity must not exceed 65%. In addition, the carbon concrete must not be exposed to direct or alternating moisture penetration or freeze-thaw cycles. The number of strengthening layers to be applied depends on the required increase in load-bearing capacity and the type of reinforcement used, but must not exceed four layers and 430 kN/m force. The spacing between the layers and between the layers and the existing concrete must be at least 3 mm for Type 1 and 5 mm for Type 3. In addition to the tension arrangement, a compression arrangement is also permitted. In this case, however, no forces must be assigned to the reinforcement.

An extension of the current approval is currently being prepared to allow the application of the approval beyond this, e.g. in bridge construction under loads that are not predominantly static (Riegelmann et al., 2021). Non-approved applications are possible in approvals for individual cases and have already been implemented in this way, e.g. for the reinforcement of bridges, shells or silos. Further information can be found in (Erhard et al., 2015; Hentschel et al., 2019; Steinbock et al., 2021; Weiland et al., 2013).

DESIGN BASIS

For the design of reinforced concrete structures with carbon concrete strengthening, the following known calculation measures shall be carried out in accordance with the shotcrete construction method:

- bending,
- shear force,
- composite joint
- concrete cover separation
- End anchorage
- Serviceability limit state
- Fire resistance
- Constructive design

The flexural design is usually decisive for the number of layers of carbon grids required and the associated layer thickness. The mechanical model is based on the established procedures for reinforced concrete. The assumptions made are that the cross-section remains uniform (Bernoulli hypothesis), the complete bond between the layers, the neglect of the concrete tensile strength and the usual stress-strain lines for concrete, steel and carbon reinforcement according to (DIBt, 2021).

The component resistance is determined iteratively by varying the strain plane in the section until the internal and external internal forces are in equilibrium, as shown in Eq. 1. A tensile component for the carbon reinforcement is assigned to the strengthening layer.

$$0 = N_{Ed} + F_{s1d} + F_{tex} - F_{s2d} - F_{cd} \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

In addition, the moment equilibrium can be established at the level of the carbon reinforcement, see Eq. 2.

$$M_{Ed,tex} - N_{Ed} \cdot z_{tex,1} = F_{s2d} \cdot z_{tex,s2} + F_{cd} \cdot z_{tex} - F_{s1d} \cdot z_{tex,s1} \quad \text{Eq. 2}$$

The 5 unknown forces N_{Ed} , F_{cd} , F_{s1d} , F_{s2d} and the corresponding lever arms z in Eq. 1 and Eq. 2 are determined by geometric relations of the strain distribution, see Eq. 3, Eq. 4 and Eq. 5. This provides an unambiguous solution for the equilibrium.

$$\varepsilon_{s1} = \varepsilon_{c2} + (\varepsilon_{tex} + \varepsilon_{tex,0} - \varepsilon_{c2}) \cdot \frac{d_s}{d_{tex}} \quad \text{Eq. 3}$$

$$\varepsilon_{s2} = \varepsilon_{c2} + (\varepsilon_{s1} - \varepsilon_{c2}) \cdot \frac{d_2}{d_s} \quad \text{Eq. 4}$$

$$\varepsilon_{tex,0} = \varepsilon_{s10} + (\varepsilon_{s10} - \varepsilon_{c20}) \cdot \frac{z_{tex,s1}}{d_s} \quad \text{Eq. 5}$$

The force in the carbon reinforcement is given by Eq. 6.

$$F_{tex,d} = A_{tex} \cdot \varepsilon_{tex} \cdot E_{tex} \quad \text{Eq. 6}$$

The stress and strain distributions and the equivalent forces used to determine the equilibrium are shown in Figure 2. In the design, for reasons of economy, it is intended that the carbon reinforcement reaches its ultimate strain and is thus utilised to the maximum. In addition, a notional pre-strain must be considered to account for the degree of utilisation of the old concrete section. This will affect the failure mode, the strain distribution and the area of reinforcement required. A detailed description of the determination of the flexural capacity of carbon concrete strengthened cross-sections can be found in (Frenzel, 2015) and (Curbach et al., 2017).

Figure 2: Designations on a carbon concrete strengthened cross-section taken from (Curbach et al., 2022)

CERTIFICATION

In order to carry out strengthening work in accordance with the approval, it is necessary to demonstrate suitability to carry out the work. The DIBt has therefore published the "Principles for the proof of suitability for the execution of strengthening works with carbon concrete according to the valid general type approvals" (DIBt, 2022b) for the executing companies. Companies certified according to these principles receive their proof of suitability from the GÜB (Gemeinschaft für Überwachung im Bauwesen e.V.), which is recognised for approval, and are included in a list of companies (DIBt, 2022a). To obtain certification, the company must meet the requirements described below. The site personnel must have special knowledge in the field of repair and strengthening of reinforced concrete components in accordance with the DAfStb Guideline "Protection and Repair of Concrete Components" (Deutscher Ausschuss für Stahlbeton [DAfStb], 2001) and must also be able to present an SIVV certificate (Protection, Repair, Joining and Strengthening of Concrete Components).

The certification procedure is divided into a compulsory theoretical training and examination, an optional practical training and a compulsory demonstration examination. The theoretical and practical training is carried out by CARBOCON GMBH as the approval holder on behalf of the CARBOrefit® consortium. The basics of carbon concrete as a material and the contents of the approval are taught and the practical application of the strengthening process including monitoring activities is presented. Finally, the demonstration test will be carried out by strengthening demonstration slabs and producing small-scale test specimens with evaluation by the GÜB as seen in Figure 3. In addition to the evaluation of the practical execution and the required equipment, mechanical tests will be carried out on the demonstration member and on companion specimens. These include concrete tests for flexural and compressive strength, determination of the slump and bulk density of the fine-grained concrete, determination of the bonding properties of the reinforcement in the concrete and the adhesive tensile strength.

A certificate of suitability obtained in this way is valid for three years. The theoretical part can be renewed by further training, and the practical part is demonstrated by properly executed rebar projects and documentation, and is extended by the GÜB. Proof of suitability is applied for independently by the contractors to the GÜB.

Figure 3: Applying a layer of fine-grained concrete on a demonstration slab as part of a training course (Photo: Sebastian May)

CONCLUSION

Compared to other strengthening methods, carbon concrete offers great potential for saving resources, as only small layer thicknesses are required to achieve a large increase in load-bearing capacity. With the CARBOrefit[®] method, an innovative technology has become established in the traditionally conservative construction industry, which allows the flexural strengthening of interior components within the framework of the general technical approval. This will save many existing buildings from demolition in the future, as has already been successfully demonstrated in a large number of practical projects. The CARBOrefit[®] consortium is committed to the continuous development of the approval regulations in order to expand the scope of application in the future. Training courses and certification with proof of suitability enable contractors to apply the technology themselves. In this way, the user base is continually expanded and the change in the building sector towards climate neutrality is driven forward.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

No data was assembled for the production of this paper.